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10 / 10 / 2024

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Introduction

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

MUAMMOGA ASOSLANGAN TA'LIM: TA'LIM JARAYONIDAGI YANGILIK

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola "Muammoga asoslangan ta'lim" (MAT) yondashuvining ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyatini tahlil qiladi. Muammolarni hal qilishga asoslangan ta'lim usuli talabalarni faol ishtirok etishga, kritik fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga va hamkorlikda ishlashga undaydi. Muammo va strategiyalarni aniqlash, real hayotdagi muammolarni o'rganish va simulyatsiyalar orqali talabalar o'z bilim va ko'nikmalarini amaliyotda qo'llash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi. Tadqiqotlar natijalariga ko'ra, MAT usuli talabalar uchun yuqori motivatsiya, ko'p tomonlama o'rganish va ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. Maqola muammoga asoslangan ta'limning kelajakdagi istiqbollari va ta'lim tizimida kengaytirilishi zarurligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Muammoga asoslangan ta'lim (MAT), Ta'lim jarayoni, Kritik fikrlash, Hamkorlik, O'quv jarayoni, Amaliyot, Motivatsiya, Ijtimoiy ko'nikmalar, Ta'lim metodologiyasi, O'quvchilarning faolligi.

Kirish

Muammoga asoslangan ta'lim (MAT) – bu o'quvchilarning muammolarni hal qilish jarayonida faol ishtirok etishini ta'minlaydigan ta'lim yondashuvi. An'anaviy ta'lim usullaridan farqli ravishda, MAT talabalarni faqat ma'lumot qabul qiluvchi sifatida emas, balki o'z-o'zini boshqaradigan, mantiqiy fikrlashga ega va ijodiy yechimlar izlaydigan shaxslar sifatida ko'radi. Ushbu maqolada muammoga asoslangan ta'limning nazariyasi, metodologiyasi va amaliyotdagi ahamiyati ko'rib chiqiladi.

Muammoga asoslangan ta'limning nazariyasi

MAT nazariyasi talabalarni muammolarni hal qilish jarayonida aktiv ishtirok etishga undaydi. Bu jarayon bir qancha asosiy tamoyillarga asoslanadi:

1. **Muammolarni aniqlash:** Talabalar o'zlari uchun dolzarb muammolarni aniqlashlari kerak. Bu bosqichda muammoning ahamiyatini tushunish va uni hal qilishga qiziqish tug'dirish muhimdir.

2. **Kritik fikrlash:** Muammolarni hal qilish jarayonida talabalar tanqidiy fikrlash va tahlil qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradilar. Bu ularning mantiqiy fikrlash qobiliyatlarini kuchaytiradi.

3. **Hamkorlik:** MAT talabalarni jamoalarda ishlashga undaydi, bu esa o'zaro fikr almashish va turli nuqtai nazarlarni hisobga olish imkonini beradi.

Muammoga asoslangan ta'lim metodologiyasi

Muammoga asoslangan ta'lim metodologiyasi bir qator strategiyalar va usullarni o'z ichiga oladi:

- **Muammolarni tanlash:** O'qituvchilar talabalar qiziqishlari va ta'lim yo'nalishlariga mos keladigan muammolarni tanlaydilar.

- **Case studies:** Real hayotdagi muammolarni o'rganish orqali talabalar ularni hal qilishda amaliy tajribaga ega bo'lishadi.

- **Simulyatsiyalar:** Talabalar virtual yoki real sharoitlarda muammolarni hal qilish jarayonida o'z ko'nikmalarini sinab ko'rishlari mumkin.

Amaliyotda muammoga asoslangan ta'lim

Tadqiqotlar ko'rsatadiki, muammoga asoslangan ta'lim metodlari talabalar uchun ko'plab foydalar keltiradi:

- **Yuqori motivatsiya:** Talabalar muammolarni hal qilish jarayonida o'zlarini qiziqish bilan jalb etadilar.

- **Ko'p tomonlama o'rganish:** Ular turli xil fikrlash usullarini o'rganadilar va shaxsiy tajribalaridan foydalanadilar.

- **Ijtimoiy ko'nikmalar:** Jamoaviy ish orqali talabalar muloqot va hamkorlik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradilar.

Natijalar va xulosalar

Muammoga asoslangan ta'lim usuli ta'lim jarayonini yanada samarali va qiziqarli qiladi. Talabalar nafaqat nazariy bilimlarni o'zlashtirib qolmay, balki amaliy ko'nikmalarini ham rivojlantiradilar. MAT ta'lim tizimida kengaytirilishi kerak, chunki u zamonaviy ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy muammolarni hal qilishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

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